

TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING THE DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF THE UNIVERSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534954>

Abstract. This article provides an analysis of some studies on the digital learning environment in the system of professional education of the university and clarifies the pedagogical and information technologies that are appropriate for use in this environment.

Keywords: professional training, digital learning environment, distance learning system, pedagogical technologies.

Introduction. Currently, the classical methodological base of teaching is changing, which leads to the emergence of new forms and technologies of teaching, and is due to the active use of information technology, distance learning innovations and online learning at the university. All these changes lead to the emergence of a digital educational environment of the university. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About education" pays much attention to the use of "electronic learning, distance learning technologies" [1]. It can be said that the need to create a digital educational environment is due to modern trends in education.

Methodology. The digital educational environment of the university contains a set of information resources and systems that allow solving various educational problems and improve the quality of traditional professional education: the use of blended learning, improving the quality of educational content, accessibility and openness of the material provided, support for the educational process, the presence of synchronous and asynchronous interaction [2,3].

The issue of using distance learning technologies and e-learning in professional training has been considered by many researchers. Analyzing the sources, we can say that the digital educational environment allows for lectures, practical classes, laboratory work, organizing project activities and individual lessons, carrying out automatic current, midterm, final certification, conducting dialogue on-line and/or off-line modes [4-7].

Researchers in their works, considering the issue of using the means of organizing distance educational technologies, identified the main criteria for choosing the means of organizing e-learning. The main ones include multifunctionality, reliability, stability of the system; the presence of elements and means of content development; knowledge testing systems; ease of use and accessibility; interactivity; system update [8].

Technologies. To organize e-learning in professional training, it is necessary to use software products. Such software products as Blackboard, e-College, WebCT, Moodle, Prometheus, Pruffme are oriented towards use in educational institutions. Today, the most widespread in the CIS countries is the Moodle distance learning system. The Moodle system meets the selection criteria for distance learning systems, so it has found wide application among educational institutions of various levels. At the university, Moodle is a web application located on the server, and access to it is carried out through a browser [4,6,7].

In Uzbekistan, the Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS) was launched, created within the framework of the World Bank project. HEMIS allows automating the administrative, educational and scientific activities of universities, providing modern electronic services to teachers and students, creating an information and educational corporate portal for universities. As a result, the training of personnel in the professional education system, implemented in the digital educational environment of the university, acts as a catalyst and initiator of new pedagogical processes [9].

The existing educational technologies, forms, methods and means for implementing university programs in the digital educational environment do not fully meet the social demand. A relevant way to solve the identified problems is to use modern learning models and learning technologies with the strengthening of innovative components of forms, methods and means of teaching. The theory of innovative pedagogy presents a large number of classifications of "technologies" by the authors: Sh.A. Amonashvili, N.F. Tylyzina, V.A. Slastenin, G.K. Selevko, M.V. Klarin, V.P. Bepalko, B.T. Likhacheva, V.V. Guzeeva and others. According to the direction of modernization and the relation to the traditional system, the following groups of technologies can be distinguished: by the sign of novelty (traditional and innovative); by the nature of cognitive activity (reproductive and productive). Pedagogical technologies based on the activation and intensification of students' activities (cooperative learning, personally oriented, developmental learning, game technologies, problem-based, cooperative learning, learning through communication). Pedagogical technologies based on programmed and differentiated learning, learning technologies according to an individual educational trajectory, group and collective learning methods, integrated learning, information and communication technologies, etc.

In the era of digitalization of education, innovative technologies are important. These include project-based learning technologies, problem-based learning, multi-level learning, collaborative learning, case technology, the use of game methods in learning, integrated learning, information and communication technologies, the case method, and the development of critical thinking [10].

Important in learning technologies today is the use of advanced learning technologies Advanced Learning Technologies (ALT). ALT is a technology based on the fusion of "learning" and "e-learning". This is a completely new format of learning aimed at improving the educational process, which incorporates traditional pedagogy and innovations in technologization. These include individual needs and abilities of the student, individual learning paths, virtual, augmented reality, simulators, intelligent learning environments, etc. At the junction of "E-learning" and "EdTech" comes online learning; flexible and adaptive learning; learning based on the interaction of teachers and students using distance learning technologies [6,8].

ALTs are classified into the following groups: established (learning process technologies based on LMS; online assessment, collaborative learning, knowledge management and joint production of new knowledge, production of educational content, video and multimedia in learning); actively developing (online learning, use of social networks in learning, adaptive and personalized learning, gamification, educational games and environments, simulators); breakthrough (big data and analytics of the educational process, artificial intelligence in learning, technologically supported methods for developing thinking skills, virtual and augmented reality in the educational process, the Internet of Things) [11].

Conclusions. Thus, the digital educational environment of the university allows implementing the educational process, providing future personnel and teachers of the university with new opportunities. Professional training of personnel in such a university system can be implemented using traditional technologies, methods, forms, training tools with the mandatory use of technologies and special training tools special for the digital educational environment.

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